

A Study on Effectiveness of Training Towards Employee with Reference to Ammarun Foundries, Coimbatore

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Abstract

This study titled “A Study on Effectiveness of Training Towards Employees with Reference to Ammarun Foundries, Coimbatore” examines the impact of training and development programs on employee performance, skill enhancement, and overall organizational productivity at Ammarun Foundries. Training plays a vital role in improving employees’ technical knowledge, efficiency, and job satisfaction in manufacturing industries.

INTRODUCTION

Training plays a vital role in enhancing the knowledge, skills, and competencies of employee, thereby contributing significantly to organizational growth and efficiency. In today’s competitive industrial environment, continuous employee training has become essential for organizations to adapt to technological advancements, improve productivity, and maintain quality standards. An effective training system not only improves employee performance but also increases job satisfaction, motivation, and commitment towards organizational goals.

Ammarun Foundries being a manufacturing-oriented organisation, relies heavily on skilled and knowledgeable employees to ensure smooth operations, safety, and product quality. In such an industry, regular training programs are crucial to upgrade technical skills, familiarize employees with modern machinery, and enhance problem-solving abilities. Well-structured training helps employees perform their duties more efficiently and reduces errors, wastage, and workplace accidents.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bhakuni & Maurya (2025) Bhakuni and Maurya found that training program significantly improve employee job performance, skill development and contribute to overall organizational growth. The study also highlights methodological gaps suggesting the need for more robust research designs in future studies.

Bose (2025) Bose examined the impact of behavioural training program on factory

employee, focusing on communication skills. This study revealed that training initiatives targeting interpersonal behaviour, teamwork, and effective **communication** enhances employees ability to convey ideas clearly collaborate efficiently and resolve workplace conflicts.

Bhandari & Kulkarni (2025) Bhandari and Kulkarni studies the relationship between training and employee engagement in manufacturing organizations. The findings revealed that well-structured training programs enhance employee skills, confidence, and sense of value within the organization, leading to higher engagement levels.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the existing training practices followed at Ammarun foundries
2. To study the effectiveness of training in improving employee job performance
3. To study how training influences employee motivation and morale

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study adopts a descriptive research design. Descriptive research is used to systematically describe the effectiveness of training programs provided to employees at Ammarun Foundries. This design helps in understanding employees’ perceptions, experiences, and outcomes of training without manipulating any variables.

Sample Design:

Sample design refers to the procedure used to select a representative group of respondents from the total population for the purpose of the

study. In this research, the sample design was carefully framed to collect reliable and relevant information regarding the effectiveness of training programs provided to employees at Ammarun Foundries, Coimbatore.

Sample Size:

Sample size refers to the number of respondents selected from the total population for the purpose of the study. In this research, the population consists of all employees working at Ammarun Foundries, Coimbatore, including shop-floor workers, technicians, supervisors, and administrative staff. The selected sample size is considered adequate to understand employees' perceptions, experiences, and views on the effectiveness of training programs conducted by the organization. The data collected from this sample helps in analyzing the impact of training on employee performance, skill development, safety awareness, and work efficiency.

Data Collection:

The purpose of this study is to collect relevant data that will help determine how effective the training programs at ammarun foundries are in improving employee skills, performance, motivation, and job satisfaction.

Primary Data:

The data focused on employees perceptions regarding training needs, quality of training programs, relevance to job roles, improvement in skills, productivity, motivation, and overall performance.

Secondary Data:

The secondary data helps in understanding existing training practices, methods adopted and their impact on employee performance, productivity, motivation and skill development by analysing earlier research and documented information.

TOOLS FOR THE STUDY

The data collected from employees were analysed using appropriate statistical tools to understand the effectiveness of training programs. The analysis helped in identifying patterns, relationships, and differences in employee opinions regarding

training and its impact on performance. The tools used in this study are explained below:

- Simple Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square Test
- Weighted Average analysis

1. Simple Percentage Analysis

Simple percentage analysis was used to present the collected data in percentage form. It helps to understand the distribution of respondents based on demographic factors such as age, gender, education, and experience. It also shows the proportion of employees who are satisfied or dissatisfied with the training programs.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
18-25	87	57
25-30	23	15
30-40	22	14
45-50	6	4
Total	152	100

INTERPRETATION

It is Known from the above table that 57% of the respondents are in the age of 18-25 years and 15% of the respondents are in the age of 25-30 years and 14% of the respondents are in the age of 30-40 years and 4% of the respondents are in the age of 45-50 years.

INFERENCE

Thus it is evidence from the above analysis the majority 57% of the respondents belong to 18-25

2. Chi-Square Test

The Chi-Square test is used to examine whether there is a significant difference in the distribution of respondents based on gender in the study on training effectiveness at Ammarun Foundries.

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference in the distribution of respondents based on gender.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is a significant difference in the distribution of respondents based on gender.

Observed Frequency Table

Gender	Number Of Respondents
Female	112
Male	40
Others	NIL
Total	152

Expected Frequency

Total respondents =152

Number of categories =3

Expected Frequency (E) = 152/3=**50.6**

Chi-Square Calculation

GENDER	O	E	(O-E)2/E
Female	112	50.6	74.50
Male	40	50.6	2.22
Others	0	50.6	50.60
Total chi-square			127.32

Calculated value =127.32

Degree Of Freedom= 2

Table Value at 5% level=5.991

Result: Null hypothesis is rejected

INTERPRETATION

The Chi-square test was applied to analyse whether there is a significant difference in the gender distribution of respondents. The calculated Chi-square value (127.32) is much higher than the table value (5.991) at 5% level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. Since the calculated value exceeds the table value, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the number of male and female respondents. The majority of respondents are female (112), followed by male (40), while there are no respondents in the “Others” category.

Weighted Average Method

Effectiveness Level	Weight	No Of Respondents	Weighted Score
Excellent	5	59	295
Good	4	72	288
Average	3	17	51
Poor	2	4	8
Total		152	642

Weighted Average = 642/152=**4.223**

INTERPRETATION

The Weighted average score is 4.223 which indicates that the training programme is rated between good and excellent by employees.

FINDINGS

- The total number of respondents is 152. Female respondents (112) are significantly higher compared to male respondents (40).

- No respondents fall under the “Others” category.

The calculated Chi-square value (127.32) is greater than the table value (5.991).

SUGGESTION

- The organization may try to ensure balanced gender participation in future surveys or studies
- Efforts can be made to encourage participation from all gender categories for better representation.

CONCLUSION

Training and development play a vital role in improving employee performance and organizational growth in manufacturing industries. This study examined the effectiveness of training programs provided to employees at Ammarun Foundries. The findings reveal that the majority of employees have participated in training programs and perceive them as useful in enhancing their technical skills, knowledge, and work efficiency. The analysis indicates that training has contributed to better understanding of job responsibilities, improved productivity, reduced errors, and enhanced safety awareness among employees. Most respondents expressed satisfaction with the training methods, duration, and trainer support. However, there is scope for improvement in areas such as advanced skill development, regular refresher programs, and increased practical sessions.

Overall, the study concludes that training programs at Ammarun Foundries are effective in improving employee performance and supporting organizational objectives. Strengthening training strategies, incorporating modern techniques, and continuously evaluating program outcomes will further enhance employee competence, job satisfaction, and long-term organizational success.